

D8.1. Project public website

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Due Date: 31 January 2024
Delivery Date: 31 January 2024
Revision Date: 12 November 2025

Horizon Innovation Action | Agreement No. 101137227
HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05
Co-funded by the European Union

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ThrombUS+ is an Innovation Action Project co-funded by the European Union, under HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05 "Harnessing the potential of real-time data analysis and secure Point-of-Care computing for the benefit of person-centred health and care delivery".

Document Control Page

Project

Grant Agreement:	101137227
Acronym:	Thrombus+
Title:	Wearable Continuous Point-of-Care Monitoring, Risk Estimation and Prevention for Deep Vein Thrombosis
Type:	Innovation Action
Start:	1 January 2024
End:	30 June 2027
Programme:	Horizon Europe
Call Identifier:	HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05
Call Topic	Harnessing the potential of real-time data analysis and secure Point-of-Care computing for the benefit of person-centred health and care delivery
Website:	https://thrombus.eu/

Deliverable

#	01
No:	D8.1
Deliverable Title:	Project public website
Deliverable Type:	DEC
Classification:	PU
Task:	8.1
Task Leader:	SciGen [E. Briola]
Work Package:	8
Work Package Leader:	SciGen [E. Briola]
Responsible Partner:	SciGen
Authors:	E. Briola [SciGen]
Input from:	All consortium partners
Peer Reviewers:	General Assembly
Due Date:	M01 – 31 January 2024
Delivery Date:	31 January 2024
Revision Date:	12 November 2025

Document Status

Version:	2.0
Status:	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consortium reviewed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP leader endorsed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator endorsed

Revision History			
Version	Date	Modification	Contributors
0.1	23 Jan 2024	New content	E. Briola [SciGen]
1.0	30 Jan 2024	Typos and formatting	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA] E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]
2.0	12 Nov 2025	Revision based on PR1 review comments: Section 2.1.4 was updated to reflect the strategy, tools and metrics installed to monitor website engagement.	K. Pavlidi [SciGen] E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D8.1 Description

The public project website in its initial form. The website will be maintained and updated throughout the project and kept alive for at least 5 years after the end of the project. Output of Task 8.1.

Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
EU	European Union
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
MySQL	Open-source relational database management system
PHP	Server-side scripting & programming language
PPT	Microsoft® PowerPoint®
QR code	Matrix barcode for quick data retrieval using mobile devices.
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
URL	Uniform Resource Locator: web address specifying a resource's internet location
US	Ultrasound
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

The goals of this document are:

- 1| To describe actions taken for the creation of the ThrombUS+ project identity, a prerequisite for web presence, including:
 - ThrombUS+ logo
 - ThrombUS+ presentation template
 - ThrombUS+ banner.
- 2| To describe actions taken for the ThrombUS+ web presence, including:
 - project website
 - project presence in social media: X (Twitter), Facebook, LinkedIn, SlideShare, YouTube.

1. Project identity

1.1. Logo

A strong graphic identity strengthens the project's image, creating a positive and lasting impression and contributes towards an effective communication of the project's main concepts. This is even more important when dissemination addresses the general public. The graphic identity of the project starts with the project's logo, which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The ThrombUS+ project logo.

1.1.1. Logo design insight

- “Thromb” in “ThrombUS+”: Represents the concept of thrombus, i.e. a blood clot that forms within the blood vessels, and thrombosis, the medical condition that is caused by the formation of thrombi. The use of “Thromb” achieves a direct association of the logo with the medical focus of the project.
- “US” in “ThrombUS+”: Abbreviation of the compound word “ultrasound”, establishing a connection with the main diagnostic technology planned in the project.
- “+” in “ThrombUS+”: Suggests that the project involves more than just the ultrasound diagnostic technology, potentially encompassing additional medical, technological, or diagnostic elements, including the impedance plethysmography/spectroscopy, light reflection rheography, wearable and activity sensors and added-value guidance and engagement services planned in the project.
- Ultrasound Graphic: Symbolizes the use of ultrasound-based imaging technology, providing a visual cue for the diagnostic aspect of the project.

1.1.2. Color choice:

Blue-Green: Represents the color of blood within the veins, connecting the visual aspect of the logo to the medical condition being addressed (DVT).

1.2. Banner

The project banner is crafted to encapsulate the essence of the ThrombUS+ project. Within this visual display (shown in Annex 1), a series of key elements are arranged to convey the project's identity and objectives:

- ThrombUS+ logo: The central focal point of the banner is adorned with the distinctive ThrombUS+ logo, a symbol that encapsulates the initiative's mission and visual identity.
- Slogan: The project slogan was chosen to articulate the core message and values of ThrombUS+:
“A revolutionary approach to deep vein thrombosis (DVT) diagnosis and prevention, harnessing the power of cutting-edge technology and interdisciplinary collaboration”.
- Objectives: The primary objectives of the ThrombUS+ initiative are outlined.

- Partners' logos: Demonstrating collaborative efforts, the banner features logos of all ThrombUS+ consortium partners.
- Acknowledgement of EU funding: A dedicated section highlighting EU funding.
- Web domain: The web domain is prominently displayed, creating an accessible gateway for viewers to explore more about ThrombUS+.
- QR Code: Incorporated strategically, a QR code enhances interactivity by providing a quick and convenient means for viewers to access ThrombUS+ website.

2. Project public website

2.1. Website

The ThrombUS+ website:

- Hosts all project-related public information.
- Allows for key communication activities of the project.

The website is designed to present all project specific information, including:

- All public project reports, publications and presentations.
- Links to related projects, news section, etc.

2.1.1. Web domain

The project web domain was chosen to directly reflect the project's acronym and identity (i.e. European project). Thus, the project web domain is: www.thrombus.eu

2.1.2. Website implementation

The project website is implemented using the open-source platform WordPress. The criteria for the final selection took into consideration various aspects including provisions for customizable code, modular engine supported by a very large community in the forms of plugins and themes, an architecture based on user feedback and discussions and the platform's security. At the time of original implementation the website used the latest WordPress version (6.4.2), but this will be constantly updated and maintained keeping up with stable subsequent versions. The underlying software infrastructure is a combination of the Apache HTTP server, PHP and MySQL hosted by ATHENA.

2.1.3. Website structure and design

The website has been designed for 3 different target audience groups and their specific informational requirements:

- **Researchers and Innovators:** As the ThrombUS+ project involves research and innovation, a key target audience is the research community. Their informational requirements involve a concise list of all scientific breakthroughs within the project, accompanied by links to the actual tools, technologies, and software to be developed throughout the project's duration. A crucial aspect for this audience is a comprehensive list of links to scientific publications resulting from the project. Project innovations breakthroughs are planned to be presented on the "Innovation" section of the project's website.

- **Patients or healthy citizens:** The primary project outcome will be a suite of services aimed at enabling point-of-care prevention and diagnosis, self-care, and empowerment for patients with high risk of thrombosis. Informational needs for patients and health-conscious citizens revolve around a clear and straightforward presentation of the project’s goals and expected timeline, regular updates on project progress, and details on ThrombUS+ patient point-of-care and empowerment services. These requirements are fulfilled through the “For Patients” section on the project website.
- **Healthcare professionals:** One of the project’s major outcomes is decision support services for healthcare professionals, particularly in the context of DVT. The informational needs of healthcare professionals include a professional, scientifically justified description of the project’s goals and methodology, regular updates on project advancements, and information on ThrombUS+ decision support services. This information is accessible through the “For Professionals” section on the project website.

ThrombUS+ Website Sitemap

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the <https://thrombus.eu/> sitemap, depicting the categories of 1st and 2nd levels.

The navigation of the website is organized to a maximum of three levels. The overall structure consists of 4 main regions:

- **Project:** Information on the ThrombUS+ project
- **Innovation:** Providing researchers with comprehensive details and links for accessing project’s publications and technological advancements, such as source code, software, tools, and services.
- **For patients:** Delivering information to patients about thrombosis and the anticipated outcomes of the project. This segment will be fully operational in 2025, coinciding with the availability of the initial project results.
- **For professionals:** Offering healthcare professionals information on the latest medical evidence for managing DVT and highlighting project outcomes. This section will be launched later in 2025 (M018), aligning with the release of the project’s initial findings.

Additionally, there are links to an interactive calendar for project-related events, project contacts, and the private members’ website (for project collaboration, see D.1.1.) The sitemap including the 1st and 2nd link levels is shown in Figure 2.

2.1.4. Website promotion & analytics

The project website is promoted by:

- search engine optimization (SEO);
- addition of links or references on ThrombUS+ partners' websites;
- project's dissemination material, such as brochures, presentations, press-releases, where the website URL must be highlighted.

The ThrombUS+ website implements the Google Analytics API in order to keep track of site usage and other analytics like demographic information. These statistics will be made available during progress reports, in forthcoming deliverables, and on demand.

Google Analytics provides comprehensive metrics on visitor engagement, including

- page views,
- session duration,
- bounce rates, and
- user flow patterns across the website.

Google Analytics also tracks

- geographical distribution of visitors,
- device types, and
- traffic sources,

enabling the consortium to understand how stakeholders interact with project content and identify the most effective channels.

Key performance indicators monitored through Google Analytics include:

- the number of unique visitors,
- returning visitor rates, and
- engagement with specific content sections such as news updates and publications.

This data allows the consortium to assess the reach and impact of communication activities, optimize content strategy based on user behavior, and demonstrate tangible evidence of project visibility and stakeholder engagement. Regular analytics reports will be included in subsequent deliverables to track the evolution of website traffic and user engagement throughout the project lifecycle.

3. Social media

The project's online presence is enhanced by the inclusion of pages on various widely used social media platforms, as described below.

X (formerly known as Twitter) is an ideal platform for sharing immediate updates, news, and announcements related to the project. The project X(Twitter) account available on <https://twitter.com/ThrombUSplus> and is shown in Figure 3.

LinkedIn is a professional networking platform, making it an ideal choice to connect with other professionals, businesses, or organizations in a more formal context. The project LinkedIn page is available on <https://www.linkedin.com/company/101550153/admin/feed/posts/> and is shown in Figure 4.

Facebook has a massive and diverse user base, making it an excellent platform for reaching a broad audience. The project Facebook page is available on <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61555678573478> and is shown in Figure 5.

A YouTube and a SlideShare project account will also be set up as part of the Dissemination and Communication plan (D8.2).

Figure 3. ThrombUS+ page on X (Twitter).

Figure 4. ThrombUS+ page on LinkedIn

Figure 5. ThrombUS+ page on Facebook.

Annex 1 | Project Banner

Shaping the Future of DVT Diagnosis
Detect Early, Live Better

ThrombUS⁺

A revolutionary approach to deep vein thrombosis (DVT) diagnosis and prevention, harnessing the power of cutting-edge technology and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Objectives

Early and Autonomous DVT Detection

Continuous Monitoring for High DVT Risk Patients

Integration of AI-Driven Decision Support

Support for DVT Prevention via Serious Gaming

Extended Reality for Optimal Device Usage

Large-Scale Clinical Studies for AI Training

Partners

Fraunhofer Institute for Photonic Microsystems

Funding

Horizon Innovation Action | Agreement No. 101137227
HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05
Co-funded by the European Union

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